

Swami Vivekananda and his Philosophy in the Present Context

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ABSTRACT

January month is a significant month for the Indians. First, January is the month of the English New Year. Also, in all the Ramakrishna Missions and Maths, Kalpataru Utsav/festival is celebrated, which Ramakrishna Dev Dev initiated on January 1, 1886. In this month, Sankranti is celebrated. On January 12, 1863, Swami Vivekananda was born, and on January 23, 1997, the great son of India, Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose, was born. All Indians know Netaji's massive contribution to the freedom movement, but in the history books, only two families' enormous contributions are highlighted. Anyway, January 26 is celebrated as Republic Day. Our Republic is powerful, so we are United, but we all know how Bangladesh was created in 1971. Swami Vivekananda survived 39 years but kept an indelible mark as he popularised Vedanta and Yoga to the Western world. He is credited with raising interfaith awareness and bringing Hinduism to the status of a major world religion in the late nineteenth century. Swami Vivekananda is best known in the United States for his groundbreaking speech to the 1893 World's Parliament of Religions, in which he introduced Hinduism to the American people and called for religious tolerance. Based on secondary sources, this article highlights the activities of Swami Vivekananda. Swami Vivekananda followed Vedanta philosophy. Vedanta has three forms: Dvaita (Dualism), Vishishtadvaita (Specific Dualism), and Advaita (Monism). Vivekananda supported Advaita. According to him, there is no difference between Dvaita, Vishishtadvaita, and Advaita.

Keywords: January, Swami Vivekananda, India, Vedanta and Yoga

Introduction:

According to the 2022 revision of the World Population Prospects, the population stood at 1,407,563,842. India has more than 50 percent of its population below the age of 25 years and more than 65 percent below the age of 35. So, it is evident that the youths of India are a great strength. Always, India's youth are the vibrant force. For this, every year, January 12 is observed as National Youth Day, which is the birthday of India's selfless and great saint, Swami Vivekananda. In 1984, the Government of India declared this day National Youth Day, and since 1985, the same has been celebrated in India every year. January month is a significant month for the Indians. First, January is the month of the English New Year. Also, in all the Ramakrishna Missions and Maths, Kalpataru Utsav/festival is celebrated, which Ramakrishna Dev initiated on January 1, 1886. In this month, Sankranti is celebrated. On January 12, 1863, Swami Vivekananda was born, and on January 23, 1997, the great son of India, Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose, was born. All Indians know Netaji's massive contribution to the freedom movement, but in the history books, only two families' enormous contributions are highlighted. Anyway, January 26 is celebrated as Republic Day. Our Republic is powerful, so we are United, but we all know how Bangladesh was created in 1971.

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Activities of Swami Vivekananda:

Swami Vivekananda was born on January 12, 1863, in Calcutta, now Kolkata. His name in school/college was Narendranath Dutta, and his parents used to call him 'Biley.' He was brilliant from childhood as he was the only student to pass the first division in the Presidency College entrance examination.

To get an idea about Swamiji, a few lines are quoted here, "All power is within you, you can do anything and everything. Believe in that; do not believe that you are weak. You can do anything and everything without even anyone's guidance. Stand up and express the divinity within you. Arise, Awake, and Sleep no more. Within each of you, there is the power to remove all wants and all miseries. Believe in this, and that power will be manifested". He respected all religions in his own words, "The Christian is not to become a Hindu or a Buddhist, nor a Hindu or a Buddhist to become a Christian. But each must assimilate the spirit of the others

and yet preserve his individuality and grow according to his law of growth". He further said, "Feel like Christ, you will be a Christ; feel like Buddha, and you will be a Buddha. It is the feeling that is life, strength, and vitality, without which no intellectual activity can reach God."

He was a great believer in hard work. In his words, "It is a tremendous error to feel helpless. Do not seek help from anyone. We are our help. If we cannot help ourselves, there is none to help us. The moment you fear, you are nobody. Fear is the great cause of misery in the world".

Today, inclusive growth is talked about in our country. Swami Vivekananda long ago said, "In India, there are two great evils, trampling on the women and grinding the poor through caste restrictions." This line reveals inclusive growth. Regarding his feelings towards Indians, he said, "I am an Indian – every Indian is my brother"; Say, the ignorant Indian, the poor and destitute Indian, the Brahmin Indian, the pariah Indian, is my brother." So, with the feelings of Indians, we are proud. I, as a resource person, visited many countries and observed Indians were highly respected.

As a spiritual and social service organization, Ramakrishna Mission is popular worldwide. Swamiji is the architect who set up the Ramakrishna Mission. During natural calamities, etc., generous services rendered by the Ramakrishna Mission are known to all. Because of him, Indian yogic practices and culture gained popularity worldwide, particularly in Western countries. His famous saying (in Chicago, 1893), 'Sisters and Brothers of America,' mesmerized the world's people as he ventilated his feelings from the core of his heart without any formality.

Swamiji had to struggle to reach Chicago, but in the process, many helped him. Among many names, I wish to mention Madam Katharine Abbot Sanborn. Katharine Abbot Sanborn was a poet, teacher, humorist, farmer, and, above all, a humanist. Known as Kate, she was amiable, prominent, and sociable – precisely the person to act as hostess to Swamiji in those early days. She not only introduced him to Professor Wright and other men and women of influence but was instrumental in providing him with a well-rounded preview of the American scene.

Vivekananda was influenced by Western ideas, such as universalism, by Unitarian missionaries who collaborated with the Brahma Samaj. His initial beliefs were shaped by Brahma concepts, which included belief in a formless God and the deprecation of idolatry and a "streamlined, rationalized, monotheistic theology strongly coloured by a selective and modernistic reading of the Upanishads and of the Vedanta." He propagated that "the divine, the absolute, exists within all human beings regardless of social status." Ramakrishna Dev influenced him, and he gradually brought Narendra to a Vedanta-based worldview that "provides the spiritual practice of serving human beings as actual manifestations of God."

In 2014, the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) declared June 21 as the International Day for Yoga. The idea was to celebrate the ancient Indian physical and spiritual practice worldwide and spread awareness of its benefits. By reading different kinds of literature, etc., it is evident that Swami Vivekananda popularised Yoga. The powerful oration of Vivekananda on the spiritual superiority of Indian religious traditions and Yoga won him the adoration of the Americans on September 11, 1893. Swami Vivekananda returned to India in 1897 amidst a warm reception from all types of people. He reached Calcutta/Kolkata after a series of lectures nationwide and founded the Ramakrishna Mission on May 1, 1897, at Belur Math near Calcutta. The goals of the Ramakrishna Mission were based on the ideals of Karma Yoga, and its primary objective was to serve the poor and distressed population of the country. The Ramakrishna Mission undertook various forms of social service like establishing and running schools, colleges, and hospitals, propagating practical tenets of Vedanta through conferences, seminars, and workshops, and initiating relief and rehabilitation work nationwide.

Swami Vivekananda Yuva Shakti Mission:

The Madhya Pradesh government has approved an exciting new youth mission named after Swami Vivekananda, set to launch on January 12, 2025. This innovative programme aims to transform the lives of young people by focusing on skill development, education, and social participation. The mission has three core goals: improving youth income, ensuring education completion, and encouraging social engagement. With an ambitious target of 70 percent youth participation by 2030, this initiative promises to be a game-changer for the state's younger generation. Its primary objectives are to build self-confidence among the youth, enhance skills, and prepare them for competitive challenges. Also, to promote activities that develop and showcase their talents. The mission focuses on three main components: Dialogue, Ability, and Prosperity, designed to ensure a holistic approach to empowering the youth, the release read. The Swami Vivekananda Yuva Shakti Mission has outlined three key youth empowerment goals. The first goal is to ensure that the income level of every youth meets or exceeds the rate of a minimum-skilled category worker. Second, every youth must complete education up to Class 12. The third goal is to encourage youth participation in social initiatives for the betterment of society. The mission aims for 70 percent participation by 2030.

About his Maha Samadhi (Passed away):

Swami Vivekananda attained Mahasamadhi (passed away) on July 4, 1902. He woke up early, went to Belur Math, and meditated there for around three hours. After taking classes and discussing a planned Vedic college in Ramakrishna Math, he went to his room at 7 pm and asked not to be disturbed. He left for the heavenly abode at 9:10 PM while meditating.

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